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Experiences of Junior High School Students in the Distance Learning Environment

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Abstract: The instantaneous shift from face-to-face to blended learning modality challenged students to remain resolute despite the adversities brought by the pandemic. Schools started to conduct distance learning classes using different modalities in adherence to Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). This research determined the experiences of Junior High School students in the distance learning environment. The paper describes the experiences, difficulties, and coping strategies of a group of purposively selected Junior High School students (n=30) in an urban public school exposed to various distance learning modalities. Mixed method design was used; both qualitative and quantitative data were collected through an online survey platform. The researcher used an instrument composed of 18 open-ended questions divided into four sections, namely, data privacy, basic information of respondents, open-ended questions about the thoughts and experiences of students for the past two years, and a four-point Likert scale in rating statements about their feelings and sensations; mean was used to analyze the responses in the rating scale. Frequency and percentage distribution were utilized to describe the ages and sex at birth of the respondents. Content and thematic analysis were used to analyze the qualitative data. The findings showed that the top difficulties of the students concerning their studies are the following: difficulty in doing self-learning, which means the ability to do self-regulated learning, internet connection, lack of gadgets, confusion, ability to understand the directions or instructions in modules by themselves. Other difficulties are lack of guidance from parents, stress, comprehension level, sadness, expectations from others, family challenges, load expenses, power interruption, boredom, and laziness in submitting outputs. The topmost feelings and sensations experienced by the respondents concerning their studies were worry, stress, and tiredness, which greatly affected their studies. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that teachers engaged in digital pedagogy investigate the psychological aspects of learning that could deter the academic performance of students as the benefits of distance learning and digital pedagogy become widely recognized.

Keywords: *struggling readers, reading program, needs-based intervention*

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Introduction

The Experiences of Junior High School Students in the Distance Learning Environment is an important study because the 2019 pandemic situation challenged the readiness of every school to continue the implementation of K to 12. Statistics show that there are more than 1.6 billion learners, which is nearly 80% of the world's population, that were affected by school closures both in the primary and secondary levels (UNESCO, 2020). This resulted in many challenges, including an increase in drop-out rates and lower academic performance and achievement of students, challenges that are being experienced by schools in the Philippines. The closure of public schools prompted authorities to adopt a blended learning modality to cater to all the students in the marginalized communities where the majority of students belonged. The main concerns that emerged are lack of gadgets, internet connectivity, data load allowance, lack of mastery of the online platform, and how well the students understand the lesson using blended modality. The instantaneous shift from face-to-face to blended learning modality intensified the problems in most public schools. Schools started to conduct online classes and modular classes in adherence to the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) that covers the essential requirements of education in times such as a pandemic. However, most students showed different emotions like confusion, pressure, nervousness, worry, and the like because of the unanticipated shift to blended learning modality without giving proper training to students on how they will do it. The first year of blended learning became challenging, especially for those students who could not afford to buy a gadget, had limited internet connectivity and data load allowance, and did not have the ability to study independently using digital and printed modules. These problems resulted in worry and stress among learners. The researcher believed that the authorities and leaders should conduct programs to achieve positive mental health among students to prepare them for face-to-face learning and to address the negative thoughts they obtained during the past two years. The schools have no idea about the experiences of the students for the past two years during the time of the pandemic.

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to investigate the experiences of junior high school students in the distance learning environment over the past two years. More specifically it addressed the following research question/s:

1. *What difficulties did the students encounter during the past two years of distance learning?*
2. *What were the means of coping used by the students to manage their difficulties?*

Methodology

Design

The research design used for the study was mixed methods. This design was chosen because the data is quantitative and qualitative. According to Efron and Ravid (2013), descriptive research characterizes the current conditions of the topic under investigation without trying to influence or manipulate them. In light of this, the researcher found the descriptive method more appropriate to describe the experiences and feelings of the

students and their ways of coping with difficulties over the past two years.

Participants

The target population of the study was the group of Grade 10 students in the Junior High School. It is composed of 116 males and 103 females and had a total of 219 students; they are divided into five sections that chose modular, modular-messenger, and fully online classes.

Participants of the study included in the modular class were two males. In the Modular messenger class, there were six males and 12 females. The full online class had seven males and three females. All in all, there were 30 respondents in this study with the number of male and female respondents being equal.

They were selected using random sampling using the fishbowl draw technique to randomly choose 30 respondents from the three classes: modular, modular-messenger, and full online. Before the conduct of the study, the researcher sought approval from the Division Office in the locality and the school head.

Figure 1

Profile of the Respondents According to Sex at Birth by Learning Modality

To ensure the welfare of the research participants, consent forms were personally accomplished by their guardians or parents. The researcher observed data privacy in gathering the data by using initials instead of the real names of the respondents.

Instruments

To collect data for the study, the researcher used 18 open-ended questions and a four-point Likert scale in rating the responses of the respondents.

The research questions utilized by the researcher are a type of open-ended questions. This instrument was divided into four sections in the Google Forms. The first section is about data privacy and confidentiality, the second section is about the basic information of the respondents such as their initials, age, sex at birth, grade level, mode of learning used for the past two years, and the mode of learning used in the present. To collect the qualitative data of the respondents, the third section is composed of open-ended questions such as their thoughts and feelings for the past two years, the difficulties they encountered for the past two years and difficulties in the mode of learning, percentages of class attendance, reasons for being absent, and number and allotted time for submitting assignments. The fourth section is for collecting the quantitative data in the study using a four-point Likert scale (Not at all (1), Some of the time (2), Most of the time

(3), All the time (4)). The items asked how often they experienced feelings/sensations such as anxiety, depression, disappointment, fear, stress, etc. in relation to their studies over the past two years.

Validation

The instrument was validated by the course professor who is a research expert. To improve the instrument, it was pilot tested and was checked and validated during four consultation meetings; it also underwent four revisions. The researcher revised some items to make the respondents feel comfortable in answering the questionnaire. The last item in the questionnaire is about how they feel in answering the survey, to make sure that they are comfortable in expressing their thoughts and ideas.

Administration

The instrument was administered to the respondents through Google Forms. The survey questionnaire was administered after the participants' class hours and was sent to their Messenger account through a Google Form. The respondents sent a screenshot of the receipt of the Google Form link to the researcher to ensure that they already answered it. This also allowed the researcher to easily track if all the respondents were able to answer the survey.

Procedure

The following steps were undertaken in order to collect data for the study. The researcher requested permission from the school's division superintendent to conduct the study by submitting the research proposal. The researcher also secured written permission from the principals to distribute the researcher-made questionnaire using Google Forms. The researcher distributed the survey questionnaire before the retrieval to give enough time for the respondents to answer the questionnaire. After the respondents sent a Google Form receipt through Messenger, the researcher tabulated the data by downloading the .csv or Excel file of their responses in the Google Forms.

Data Analysis

Data analysis techniques applied were meant to analyze the responses in the rating scale. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe the ages and sex at birth of the respondents. Content and thematic analysis were used by the researcher to analyze the qualitative data. Frequency and percentage were used by the researcher to count the repeating codes to construct themes. The researcher also indicated sample responses of the respondents to describe each theme.

Difficulties of students concerning studies

The first research question was about the difficulties the students encountered during the past two years of distance learning.

To answer this research question, the researcher analyzed item number 8 regarding the difficulties the students encountered for the past two years in relation to two subparts: 8.A (Difficulty about staying at home) and 8.B (Difficulties with the mode of distance learning). Section 4 number 14 is the four-point Likert scale about the feelings and sensations they experienced in relation to their studies; it was analyzed using the mean. Analysis was performed using content and thematic analysis. The researcher used

frequency and percentage to count the repeating codes in each response to construct themes. Themes are arranged in a table using ranks to identify the most repeated codes/patterns. Results in Table 1 show that the difficulties of students in distance learning in relation to staying at home for the past two years are the fear of Covid (53.33%), demotivated to study (3.33%), household chores responsibility (20%), home environment is not a good learning environment and it affects their online participation in class because of many disruptions and technical issues like internet connection and lack of gadget (16.67%), the complexity of modules, noisy place and lack of focus (13.33%), laziness (10%), untoward incidents, and no parental guidance (3.33%). The school authorities should provide technical assistance to provide students with smooth and reliable internet connection to avoid internet and technical problems (Yan et al., 2021).

Table 1

Difficulties of Students in Distance Learning about Staying at Home for the Past Two Years

Theme(s)	Code(s)	Frequency	%	Rank
Fear of Covid	nahawaan mahahawa scared freaks di makalabas	16	53.33	1
Demotivated	boring empty not having fun stressful alone	10	33.33	2
Household chores responsibility	waking up early household chores madaming ginagawa obliged house	6	20.00	3
Technical	Poor connection Electricity lost Weak connection Timer	5	16.67	4
Complexity of modules	Overloaded Not getting the activity	4	13.33	5
Noisy place	quiet place irritation distractions	4	13.33	6
Lack of focus	can't focus distractions gadgets	4	13.33	7
Laziness	boring lazy	3	10.00	8
Untoward Incidents	Fire, flood	1	3.33	9
No Parental Guidance	No one to monitor	1	3.33	10

As we can glean from Table 2, the difficulties of students with the mode of distance learning are difficulty in understanding the lesson (53.33%). Next are the internet connection (43.33%),

unclear instruction, lack of focus, guidance, acquaintance, stress, and anxiety (6.67%). Other difficulties are grasping lessons, sadness, expectations, challenges, load expenses, power interruption, noncompliance, and boredom (3.33%).

Table 2*Difficulties of Students with the Mode of Distance Learning*

Theme(s)	Code(s)	Frequency	%	Rank
Understanding lesson	hard time understand slow not hard not easy	16	53.33	1
Internet connection	connection lack of internet not stable no Wi-Fi	13	43.33	2
Confusions in instruction	clear instruction prediction hardly to understand nakakalito	2	6.67	3
Lack of focus	no focus	2	6.67	4
Guidance	guidance of teacher	2	6.67	5
Acquaintance	too shy hard to get a friend	2	6.67	6
Stress	difficult anxiety stress	2	6.67	7
Grasping of lesson	failed to do activities walang maintindihan not explained well	1	3.33	8
Sadness	sad	1	3.33	8
Expectations	higher expectation	1	3.33	8
Challenges	hindi ko alam ang gagawin not getting the lesson fast	1	3.33	8
Load expenses	no money	1	3.33	8
Power interruption	electricity lost	1	3.33	8
Noncompliance	can't submit	1	3.33	8
Boredom	really boring	1	3.33	8

Figure 2 shows the feelings and emotions of the respondents from the highest to the lowest rank. Worry is the highest emotion with a 2.80 mean, next is stress with a 2.77 mean, tiredness with a 2.67 mean, nervousness with a 2.60 mean, fear with a 2.53 mean, sleeplessness with a 2.40 mean, laziness with a 2.37 mean, lack of energy and loneliness with a 2.27 mean, insecurity with a 2.13 mean, disappointment and sadness with a 2.10 mean, irritation and lack of interest with a 2.03 mean, anxiety with a 2.00 mean, feeling sick with a 1.73 mean, depression with a 1.67 mean and, the least in the rank is lack of appetite with a 1.63 mean.

Figure 2

Feelings and Sensations of Respondents for the Past 2 years in Relation to Their Studies

Ways of coping for students

The second research question was about the means of coping used by the students to manage their difficulties.

To answer this research question, the researcher analyzed item number 15, which is about how the participants cope and manage their negative thoughts and feelings and the things they do to handle them. Item number 16A is a close-ended question answerable by Yes or No, whether there is a person that helped them overcome or manage their difficulties; 16B is a mark all test where they would choose the people that helped them while 16C is how the persons they chose in 16B helped them. Analysis was performed using content and thematic analysis where the researcher used frequency and percentage to count the repeating codes in each response to come up with the themes. Also, the researcher indicated sample responses of the respondents to describe each theme. Themes are arranged in a table using ranks to identify the most repeated codes/patterns. Results showed that the persons helped the respondents with their difficulties in their studies. The data in Figure 2 show that parents, siblings, and family members are the people who helped them the most with school activities and tasks (40%), followed by classmates, schoolmates, friends, and neighbors which (39%); 13% of the respondents said that their teachers guided them in answering their activities while 6% said that they do their school activities and tasks. Lastly, 2% of the respondents said that members of organizations helped them with their difficulties.

Figure 3

The Persons that Helped the Respondents Manage Their Difficulties and Negative Feelings

Based on Table 3, most of the difficulties of students with the mode of distance learning are difficulty in understanding the lesson (33%), internet connection (43.33%), and unclear instructions, lack of focus, guidance, acquaintance, and stress and anxiety (6.67%). Other difficulties are poor comprehension, sadness, expectation, challenges, load expenses, power interruption, noncompliance, and boredom (3.33%).

Table 3

Persons' Ways of Helping Students with Their Difficulties with the Mode of Distance Learning

Students Learning Partner	Ways on helping	Examples of student's responses
Teacher	Encourage Making Happy Entertain	and lift each other up for us to cope with the stress we are feeling. Asks each other if how we solve this and Teacher can make me feelings better by just saying "you can do it, how your feelings today my; and always be there if I need them friends can make me happy or forget the problems i have; encouraging me
	Motivate Explain and clarify instructions in the assignment	

Table 4 shows that students' coping mechanisms are talking and hanging out with friends (33.33 %), watching TV series or movies and doing meditation (23.33%), playing, listening to music, eating, and buying foods (16.66%), playing online games and doing other hobbies (13.33%), bonding with family, going to the mall, and online shopping (10%), and sleeping (2%).

Table 4

Students' Ways of Coping to Manage Their Feelings and Difficulties in Relation to Studies

Theme(s)	Code(s)	Frequency	%	Rank
Talking and hanging out with friends	talk to friends. hanging out phoning chatting calling	10	33.33	1
Watching TV and movies	watch movies	7	23.33	2
Meditation	thinking relaxing positive side breathing technique get energy	7	23.33	2
Praying/determination	pandemic is test God	5	16.66	3
Playing and listening to music	listening to music videos play	5	16.66	3
Eating and buying foods	treat self buying foods stress eating	5	16.66	3
Playing online games	online games playing	4	13.33	4
Doing hobbies like reading and cycling	doing what I like cycling reading k-drama anime	4	13.33	4
Ignoring problems	forget the problems	4	13.33	4
Bonding with family	playing dream	3	10	5
Going to mall and online shopping	going to mall shopping reward	3	10	5
Sleeping	sleep nap	2	2	86

Discussion

Summary

The study showed that the top difficulties of the students in relation to their studies are the following: difficulty in doing self-learning or the inability to do independent study, internet connection and lack of gadgets, and confusion or inability to understand the directions and

instructions in modules by themselves. Other difficulties are lack of guidance from parents, stress, comprehension level, sadness, people expectations, family challenges, load expenses, power interruption, boredom, and laziness in submitting outputs. The topmost feelings and sensations experienced by the respondents in relation to their studies are worry, stress, and tiredness, which greatly affect their studies.

The study showed that family members are the top persons that help students with their difficulties, followed by friends, classmates, and teachers. The respondents' ways of coping are the following: talking with family members, hanging out with friends, watching TV series and movies, doing meditation, playing and listening to music, eating and buying food, playing online games and doing other hobbies, bonding with family, going to the mall, online shopping, and sleeping. These are what the respondents do to manage their feelings and sensations with regard to their studies and the difficulties they encounter.

Conclusion

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the topmost difficulties of the students in relation to their studies are cognition, self-learning ability, technical and internet availability, and complicated instructions in learning materials. Cognition is the ability of the student to understand the lesson, directions, and instructions in the activity without anyone's guidance except the help of self-learning modules. Self-learning ability is the skill of the students to delve into and explore things in relation to their studies. Technical and internet availability is also a problem for most of the students, especially in areas that have poor internet connectivity. Complicated instructions in modules are another concern of the respondents, and it may be because of the respondents' lack of mastery of the lesson so they couldn't understand what they needed to do in the task.

Social life is very important in the life of the students, and open communication with parents and family members is a great help to make them strong and resilient, especially during challenging times. It is also important to stay positive and have a resilient mind to overcome any kind of difficulties. In addition, doing some recreation and leisure will help the person maintain their mental health to stay focused, persistent, and productive in their studies.

Recommendation

In light of the conclusions derived from the findings, it is recommended that first, academic departments should design a curriculum tailored to fit the pandemic situation. Prepare appropriate materials for each modality; self-learning modules should be based on the chosen modality of the students and the ability of the students to do self-learning. Create innovative materials that will engage and encourage students to learn. Coordinate with LGUs and other stakeholders for other issues like data load allowance and gadgets. School authorities may create programs and projects that will teach students to do self-study and practice self-regulation, which may be incorporated in Homeroom classes.

The school may conduct a test for every student to know their mental health status, especially for those students who had a case of self-isolation and anxiety that started during the pandemic. At the same time, they may conduct a program for the students to teach them to cope with stress, social isolation due to the pandemic, and anxiety in preparation for the new face-to-face set-up of schools. Schools may also conduct programs for the home learning partners in honing, supporting, and preparing children for their studies during challenging situations.

References

- Efron, S., & Ravid, R. (2013). *Research in Education: a practical guide*. New York, NY 10012
- Henaku, E.A. (2020). *Covid-19: Online Learning Experience of College Students: The case of Ghana*. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences and Advanced Technology*, 1, (2), 54-62
- UNESCO. 1.3 billion learners are still affected by school or university closures, as educational institutions start reopening around the world, says UNESCO (2020, April 29). Retrieved May 1, 2022, from <https://en.unesco.org/news/13-billion-learners-are-still-affected-school-university-closures-educational-institutions>
- Yan, L., Wainwright, A.W., Guan, Q., Wen, G., Gasevic, D., & Chen, G. (2021). *Student's experience of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: A province-wide survey study*. *British Journal of Educational Technology*. 2021; 52:2038–205doi:10.1111/bjet.13102